

Differential rice cultivar reactions to *Xoo* strains.

Group	Strain (no.)	Range of av lesion length and disease reaction ^a					Race designation
		IR8 (<i>Xa-11</i>)	IR20 (<i>Xa-4</i>)	IR1545-339 (<i>xa-5</i>)	CAS209 (<i>Xa-10</i>)	DV85 (<i>xa-5</i> , <i>Xa-7</i>)	
<i>Indian strains</i>							
	86						
Group 1a	5	13.0-28.0 (S)	3.0- 7.0 (R)	13.0-20.0 (S)	33.0-40.0 (S)	7.0- 9.0 (R)	Ia
Group 1b	27	16.0-24.0 (S)	10.0-15.0 (S)	11.0-17.0 (S)	31.0-40.0 (S)	7.0- 8.5 (R)	Ib
Group 2	38	19.0-23.0 (S)	11.0-17.0 (S)	17.0-21.0 (S)	20.0-39.0(S)	31.0-36.0 (S)	II
Group 3	2	10.0-18.0 (S)	3.0- 7.5 (R)	14.0-25.0 (S)	19.0-43.0 (S)	23.0-40.0 (S)	III
Group 4	3	11.0-23.0 (S)	3.0- 3.5 (R)	3.0- 9.0 (R)	23.0-46.0 (S)	6.0- 8.0 (R)	IV
Group 5	11	1.0- 3.5 (R)	1.0- 4.0 (R)	3.0- 5.0 (R)	1.0- 4.0 (R)	1.0- 5.0 (R)	-
<i>Nepalese strains</i>							
	36						
Group 1a	7	10.4-16.0 (S)	2.1- 7.7 (R)	10.3-21.7 (S)	10.5-24.6 (S)	3.0- 7.6 (R)	Ia
Group 1b	0	(S)	(S)	(S)	(S)	(R)	Ib
Group 2	7	10.2-23.0 (S)	10.6-21.0 (S)	10.9-20.4 (S)	11.6-24.1 (S)	13.9-25.9 (S)	II
Group 3	8	10.9-21.3 (S)	1.8-6.3 (R)	13.0-19.6 (S)	14.8-19.3 (S)	14.8-22.1 (S)	III
Group 4	1	10.5 (S)	2.2 (R)	5.1 (R)	10.3 (S)	7.6 (R)	IV
Group 5	11	1.3- 8.4 (R)	1.0- 2.7 (R)	1.4- 6.1 (R)	2.2- 9.6 (R)	1.4- 9.4 (R)	-
NX0200	1	6.8 (R)	2.1 (R)	3.6 (R)	12.4 (S)	10.6 (S)	-
NX0216	1	10.5 (S)	5.5 (R)	7.5 (R)	10.8 (S)	13.6 (S)	-

^aR = resistant (<10-cm lesion length), S = susceptible (>10-cm lesion length).

Integrated pest management—insects

Effects of neem and nochi on rice bug *Leptocorisa acuta*

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We conducted a field experiment using IR20 to study the effects of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) and *Vitex negundo* (nochi)

Effect of botanical pest control products on rice bug populations. Madurai, India, 1991-92.

Treatment	Rice bug (no./5 net sweeps) ^a	Decrease over control (%)
Malathion 0.05%	4.0	86.2
Neemark 0.5%	5.0	82.8
Neem oil 2.0%	9.0	69.0
Nochi leaf extract 2.5%	14.3	50.7
Nochi leaf extract 5.0%	18.0	38.0
Neem seed kernel extract 5.0%	17.7	39.0
Control	29.0	-
CD (P = 0.05)	2.54	

^aMean of three replications.

botanical pest control products on rice bug during the second season (Sep 1991-Feb 1992). The insecticide malathion 50 EC was included for comparison (see table). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with 20-m² plots and three replications.

Twenty-four hours after spraying, rice bug populations were assessed as the

Developmental biology and host plant range of rice-feeding tiger moth *Cretonotus gangis* (L.)

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We studied the development of *C. gangis* on 20 common plant species from families Poaceae (14), Cyperaceae (5), and Commelinaceae (1). Unfed neonate larvae were placed on 25- to 30-d-old individual host plants in 20-cm-diam clay pots enclosed in 10- × 72-cm cylindrical mylar cages with top and side vents of nylon mesh (1 mm²). Ten larvae were released per cage. Each cage served as a treatment, replicated 10 times, in a randomized complete block design in a

number of bugs/five sweeps of a net. Only four rice bugs were recorded in the malathion-sprayed plot, which had a population reduction of 86.2% compared with the control. The next best treatment was Neemark, with 5 bugs. Neem oil, neem seed kernel extract, and nochi were much less effective than malathion and Neemark. ■

non-airconditioned headhouse. Temperature averaged 26.9 ± 1.06 °C. Relative humidity averaged 73.2 ± 4.0%. Host suitability was determined as percentage of larval survival, larval developmental period, larval growth index, and eggs laid by emerging females.

Fecundity was determined on an individual basis for newly emerged moths, which were held in a 65- × 65- × 110-cm rectangular wooden cage frame with sides of nylon mesh (1 mm²). Honey solution (10%) was provided for food. A male was introduced for each caged female.

C. gangis survived to pupation on all 20 plant species, confirming the polyphagous nature of this insect.

Table 1. Host plant range of *C. gangis*. IRRI headhouse, Feb-Mar 1990.^a

	Parameter				Overall ranking ^f
	Larval survival (%) ^{b,c}	Larval developmental period (d) ^d	Larval growth index (rating) ^e	Eggs laid (no./female)	
Poaceae					
TN1 rice	79.0 ± 9.5 a	22.1 ± 0.8 a	3.5 ± 0.4 a	46.7 ± 40.7 a	1
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	73.0 ± 20.0 ab	23.7 ± 1.4 b	3.1 ± 0.9 ab	45.8 ± 12.5 a	2
Maize	69.9 ± 12.0 abc	29.4 ± 0.9 c	2.8 ± 0.5 bc	25.5 ± 18.9 c-g	3
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	63.0 ± 26.3 abc	30.2 ± 1.6 d	2.4 ± 1.0 cd	34.1 ± 9.3 a-e	4
<i>E. glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook f.	67.0 ± 18.3 abc	30.6 ± 0.9 e	2.5 ± 0.7 bcd	36.2 ± 7.3 a-d	5
<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	72.0 ± 18.7 ab	31.5 ± 1.8 ef	2.8 ± 0.7 bc	21.5 ± 5.6 d-h	6
<i>Isachne globosa</i> L.	53.0 ± 46.4 c	31.5 ± 1.0 ef	2.0 ± 1.8 de	49.5 ± 38.9 a	7
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	57.0 ± 22.1 bc	36.1 ± 1.2 fg	1.7 ± 0.7 ef	29.2 ± 15.8 b-f	8
<i>P. conjugatum</i> Berg.	31.3 ± 16.0 d	29.1 ± 1.2 c	1.2 ± 0.6 h	36.7 ± 13.7 a-d	9
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	24.1 ± 23.2 de	31.5 ± 1.2 ef	0.9 ± 0.9 ghi	44.7 ± 6.7 ab	12
<i>Brachlaria mutica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf.	15.0 ± 7.1 def	37.7 ± 0.9 gh	0.4 ± 0.2 ij	17.7 ± 7.1 e-h	13
<i>B. distachya</i> (L.) Stapf.	12.1 ± 11.4 ef	38.1 ± 1.4 gh	0.4 ± 0.3 ij	16.2 ± 12.5 fgh	14
<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	10.0 ± 0.0 ef	38.1 ± 1.2 gh	0.2 ± 0.0 j	17.8 ± 1.7 e-h	15
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i> (L.) Beauv	8.0 ± 4.2 ef	42.1 ± 1.6 i	0.2 ± 0.0 j	6.1 ± 6.0 h	18
Cyperaceae					
<i>Cyperus kyllingia</i> Endl.	57.2 ± 24.5 bc	32.0 ± 1.6 f	1.7 ± 0.8 ef	38.3 ± 11.7 abc	10
<i>C. brevifolius</i> (Rottb.) Hassk.	52.1 ± 24.4 c	38.1 ± 1.2 gh	1.5 ± 0.7 efg	15.9 ± 4.6 fgh	11
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.)	19.0 ± 8.8 def	35.6 ± 0.7 fg	0.6 ± 0.3 h-j	11.7 ± 4.4 gh	13
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	22.0 ± 9.2 def	43.0 ± 0.7 i	0.6 ± 0.2 h-j	33.2 ± 11.9 a-e	16
<i>C. rotundus</i> L.	4.0 ± 5.2 f	39.6 ± 1.1 h	0.1 ± 0.0 j	22.8 ± 6.3 c-g	17
Commelinaceae					
<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm. f.	4.0 ± 5.2 f	30.8 ± 0.7 e	0.1 ± 0.0 i	25.3 ± 7.0 c-g	19

^aAv of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P < 0.01) by LSD statistical test.

^bSurvival (%) = $\frac{\text{Larvae becoming pupae}}{\text{Total larvae}} \times 100$. ^cn = 100. ^dn = 10. ^eGrowth index = $\frac{\text{Larval survival (\%)}}{\text{Larval growth period (d)}}$. ^f1 = best, 19 = worst.

Table 2. Life history of *C. gangis*. IRRI headhouse, Mar-Dec 1989.^a

	$\bar{x} \pm$ SD
Egg incubation period (d)	4.6 ± 0.8
Larval stadium (d)	
I	4.5 ± 0.5
II	4.9 ± 1.3
III	4.0 ± 0.7
IV	4.7 ± 0.8
V	4.0 ± 0.5
Prepupa (d)	2.0 ± 0
Pupa (d)	8.5 ± 0.5
Total developmental period (d)	37.2 ± 1.4
Moth longevity (d)	12.0 ± 1.5
Eggs laid (no./female)	46.7 ± 40.7

^an = 100.

Highest larval survival to pupation (n = 100) occurred on rice (79%), *Leptochloa chinensis* (73%), and *Eleusine indica* (72%). The quickest larval developmental period was on rice (22.1 d), although on all other plant hosts development was significantly delayed. These two developmental parameters resulted in a high growth index for rice (3.5) and *L. chinensis* (3.1), which were significantly higher than for the other plants. Rice (TN1) was

the most suitable host (Table 1).

All the plant species served as ovipositional hosts and supported complete development of *C. gangis*. Greatest fecundity (no. eggs/female) occurred from moths reared on *Isachne globosa* (49.5), rice (46.7), *L. chinensis* (45.8), *Leersia hexandra* (44.7), *Cyperus kyllingia* (38.3), *Paspalum conjugatum*

(36.7), *E. glabrescens* (36.2), and *E. colona* (34.1) (Table 1).

Life history data for *C. gangis* developing on rice appear in Table 2.

Even though *C. gangis* is highly adapted to rice, it occurs rarely and has never been reported to be economically important. ■

Shifts in population characteristics of brown planthopper (BPH) immigrants to Japan

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Hopperburn was observed for the first time on a BPH-resistant breeding line with *Bph 1* gene in Japan in 1990, indicating that BPH immigrating to Japan may have changed significantly. This population shift was evaluated

quantitatively using 96 immigrants in 1992.

Honeydew excretion of adult females was measured individually. Insects were confined to leaf sheaths of rice at the early tillering stage with clip-on Parafilm sachets (about 1.5 × 1.5 cm) at 25 °C for 1 d. The same insects were transferred daily from resistant IR26 (*Bph 1* gene) to susceptible japonica Reihou to resistant IR42 (*bph 2* gene) to clarify the biotypic properties of individual females.

Individuals excreting at least 10 mg honeydew were tentatively classified as able to feed normally. Of the 92% that